

Development of new meat analogues from filamentous fungi cultivated on oenological by-products: A quality perspective

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ABSTRACT

Interest in the link between diet, health, and sustainable nutrition has grown, driving exploration of alternative proteins. Edible filamentous fungi offer a promising high-quality protein source for meat analogues. This study explores *Neurospora intermedia* biomass, cultivated on grape marc and wine lees produced via submerged fermentation in a demo-scale bubble column reactor, to create clean-label, vegan, and gluten-free meat analogue balls (MABs). MABs were formulated with 21.4 % (w/w) fungal protein and compared with pea-based textured vegetable protein. Protein sources were evaluated for techno-functional properties, and MABs were assessed for cooking characteristics, nutritional value, color, texture, microstructure, and sensory attributes. Fungal proteins exhibited high water (5.92–6.51 g/g) and oil (up to 5.81 g/g) absorption capacities. Fungi-based MABs had a cooking efficiency of 86.5–87.6 % and crude protein content up to 37 % on a dry basis. Texture profile analysis showed improved cohesiveness (0.63–2.23), and springiness (0.55–2.45) compared to those made from pea-based texturized proteins. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed a fibrous microstructure. Sensory evaluation under blind conditions by untrained panelists highlighted juiciness, a fibrous texture, and a fungi- or meat-aroma mimicry. These results support the potential of *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on oenological by-products as a nutritious, functional protein source for next-generation meat analogues. The study has strong potential to contribute to the circular bioeconomy fields with broader sustainability implications.

1. Introduction

With growing awareness of the environmental and health impacts of meat consumption, sustainable protein alternatives have emerged as a promising solution. These options generate up to 250 times fewer emissions than animal-based products (da Silva, Mateus, de Freitas, & Fernandes, 2024). The shift toward alternative proteins is also fueled by global protein shortages, ethical and dietary restrictions (e.g., halal, kosher, vegan, vegetarian), climate change, and economic and resource challenges (Akcan, Önel, & Ergezer, 2024; Alexander et al., 2017).

One of the rapidly growing sectors in the food industry is the meat analogue sector, which incorporates a variety of alternative protein sources. Meat analogues, also known as imitation meat, meat substitutes, mimic meat, or meat replacements, are designed to replicate the taste, texture, and appearance of conventional animal-based meat (Ahmad et al., 2022). These products are available in both raw and pre-cooked formats, including minced meat, strips, chunks, chicken-like

blocks, ground beef alternatives, steaks, ham, mortadella, sausages, burgers, patties, frankfurters, nuggets, meatballs, spreads, and even seafood alternatives (Kyriakopoulou, Keppler, & van der Goot, 2021).

The broad spectrum of alternative protein sources includes plant-based proteins, single-cell proteins (SCPs) derived from microbes such as bacteria, yeast, fungi, as well as microalgae, seaweed, edible insects, animal stem cells, and precision fermentation products (Alexander et al., 2017; Boukid & Gagaoua, 2022; Hashempour-Baltork, Khosravi-Darani, Hosseini, Farshi, & Reihani, 2020). Among these, microbial proteins, used as whole biomass or extracted protein, have garnered significant attention for their potential in food applications (Gnaim, Dyer, & Ledesma-Amaro, 2025; Wikandari, Tanugraha, Yastanto, Manikharda, & Teixeira, 2023). Mycoprotein-based products, rich in protein and fiber and low in fat, are linked to health benefits, including reduced energy intake and improved appetite regulation (Derbyshire & Delange, 2021). These products are particularly appealing to health-conscious consumers and those following vegetarian, vegan, or flexitarian diets (T.

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Finnigan, Mach, & Edlin, 2024).

A key priority in alternative protein production is applying circular economy principles by upcycling agri-food byproducts. Many of these byproducts, such as rice bran, spent brewery grain, wheat straw, potato pulp, apple pomace, banana, and citrus wastes, pineapple peel, molasses, cheese whey, prawn shells, pea byproducts, and mixed-food industry residues, have been valorized for protein production via fungal fermentation (Landeta-Salgado et al., 2024; Majumder, Miaturo, Saha, & Hossain, 2024; Ritala, Häkkinen, Toivari, & Wiebe, 2017; Salvatore, Leue-Rüegg, Beretta, & Müller, 2024; Upcraft et al., 2021). Particularly, wine and distillery byproducts, which have a significant environmental impact and contribute to the global carbon footprint, can be transformed into protein-rich fungal biomass through fungal fermentation (Hoxha, Taherzadeh, & Marangon, 2025). However, fungal products derived from agri-food side-streams bioconversion must demonstrate a verified safety profile to gain approval in Europe, emphasizing the importance of thorough risk assessment (Ballester, Roqué, Ricci-Cabello, Rotger, & Malih, 2023). Beyond safety, consumer perception and acceptance are critical when introducing fungal biomass into the human diet, particularly from side-stream sources (Chezan, Flannery, & Patel, 2022).

Several fungal-derived products are already commercially available for food applications (Souza et al., 2025). Among them, mycoproteins are receiving growing attention, particularly used in meat alternatives such as burgers, mince, and marinated pieces (Salvatore et al., 2024). Currently, mycoproteins intended for human consumption are primarily produced from filamentous fungi of the genera *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Rhizopus* (T. Finnigan et al., 2024; Gnaim et al., 2025). However, ongoing research continues to explore new fungal species with the potential to upcycle agri-food by-products without depending on synthetic glucose sources (Upcraft et al., 2021).

One promising species is *Neurospora intermedia*, a fast-growing edible filamentous fungus that has demonstrated significant potential for converting waste into food (Gmoser et al., 2020; Hellwig, Gmoser, Lundin, Taherzadeh, & Rousta, 2020; Maini Rekdal et al., 2023, 2024; Starzynska-Janiszewska, Stodolak, Dulinski, Mickowska, & Sabat, 2017). Traditionally, *N. intermedia* has been used in Indonesia for producing the meat substitute Oncom. Due to the absence of consumption history in the EU prior to May 1997, *N. intermedia* is likely considered a novel food under EU regulations and would require thorough assessment both for its quality and safety authorization before it can be authorized for commercialization in the region (European Commission, 2015). Clinical trials have been essential in demonstrating digestibility and safety before wider release. Mycoprotein is recognized as a safe food ingredient (Miller & Dwyer, 2001), and no evidence suggests adverse effects from *Neurospora* in humans or animals (Perkins & Davis, 2000). Furthermore, recent research supports its promising safety profile and its potential to expand gastronomic applications (Maini Rekdal et al., 2023, 2024).

Given the growing popularity of mycoprotein-based foods as sustainable alternatives to animal-derived proteins, this study aimed to explore the use of edible *Neurospora intermedia* biomass, cultivated on grape marc and wine lees through submerged fermentation in a demonstration-scale bioreactor, as a novel protein ingredient in vegan and gluten-free meat analogue formulations. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this represents the first investigation of this edible fungal biomass grown on oenological by-products for such applications. A comprehensive evaluation of key quality attributes was carried out on the resulting meat analogue balls (MABs), and their performance was benchmarked against a widely used commercial plant-based protein, dried pea-based textured vegetable protein (TVP), using standardized formulations to assess relative suitability and potential advantages. More broadly, the study aimed to contribute to the advancement of alternative proteins within a circular bioeconomy framework by valorizing underutilized winemaking and distillery by-products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Oenological by-products and filamentous fungus strain

Oenological by-products were collected from Acquavite distillery in Vazzola, Italy: grape marc (GM) in November 2023 and wine lees (WL) in March 2024. The GM was derived from grapes grown in the Veneto region grapes, primarily Glera skins (~80%), and was processed through seed removal, drying, and milling after fermentation and distillation. The WL originated from the subsequent wine produced from the same regional sources, and consisted of a mixture of gross and fine lees from Prosecco production. For cultivation, a 4% (w/v) GM liquor, obtained via hydrothermal pretreatment at 121 °C for 20 min, was used as liquid cultivation media. The WL were centrifuged, and the resulting liquid fraction was diluted to 50% (v/v) prior to being used as cultivation media. Both GM and WL media were supplemented with 5 g/L yeast extract and adjusted to pH 5 using 5 M NaOH (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany).

The edible filamentous fungus *Neurospora intermedia* (CBS 131.92) was used, sourced from the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute (Utrecht, Netherlands). Fungal cultivations were conducted in a 1300 L bubble column bioreactor (Knislinge Mekaniska Verkstad AB, Kristianstad, Sweden) with 1000 L working volume. The procedures for fungal biomass cultivation and harvesting, followed those described in our previous work (Hoxha, Lennartsson, & Taherzadeh, 2025). Approximately 1 L pre-culture of *N. intermedia* spores was prepared in GM or WL media in baffled Erlenmeyer flasks and incubated at 35 °C with shaking at 115 rpm for 24 h in waterbath (Grant OLS-Aqua Pro, UK). The pre-culture was transferred to a 26 L BCR (Bioengineering, Wald, Switzerland) containing 20 L of the cultivation media and incubated at 35 °C with 1 vvm (volume of air per volume of liquid per minute) aeration for 24 h. The resulting biomass suspension was transferred to the 1300 L BCR, where cultivation was incubated at 35 °C with 1 vvm aeration for 24 h. Harvested fungal biomass was washed three times with tap water, to remove residual cultivation medium (Campos, Wahalathanthrige, Russell, Harrison, & Strong, 2025), and pressed using a 12 L juice press (Bauhaus, Belp, Switzerland), then freeze-dried at 0.022 mbar with a condenser temperature of -84 °C (Labconco Free-Zone, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.). Biomass yield was determined gravimetrically, resulting in 3.290 ± 0.001 g/L for GM (Hoxha, Lennartsson, & Taherzadeh, 2025) and 4.33 ± 0.14 g/L for WL (unpublished data).

2.2. Preparation of meat analogue balls

In this study, meat analogue balls (MABs) were prepared using 21.4% (w/w) of three alternative protein sources: freeze-dried *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL), and dried pea-based textured vegetable protein (TVP). This inclusion level was determined through preliminary trials evaluating texture, as well as moisture absorption and retention, and was subsequently optimized to maintain juiciness, and prevent dryness (data not shown). Mycoprotein was benchmarked against pea TVP, a widely used ingredient in commercial meat analogues and the closest nutritional match to mycoprotein-based products (Ložnjak Švarc et al., 2022). Pea-based TVP is increasingly favored due to the demand for soy-free protein alternatives, known as a common allergen (Meinlschmidt, Schweiggert-Weisz, Brode, & Eisner, 2016), associated with GMO-related concerns, presence of anti-nutritional factors that can reduce digestibility, and may negatively influence consumer taste perceptions (Jafarzadeh et al., 2024).

The MABs preparation flow diagram is illustrated in Fig. 1. Protein ingredients were ground using a high-shear thermo-mixer (HotmixPro Gastro Master) at 3000 rpm for 30 s, then transferred to a planetary mixer (Hobart N50) for rehydration with an infusion solution containing 42.0% (w/w) cold water (4 °C) and 2.65% (w/w) clean-label spices, flavorings, and colorants (Brenntag S.p.A., Padova, Italy; Table S1).

Fig. 1. A) Flow diagram illustrating the processing of meat analogue balls (MABs) formulated with alternative protein sources, including pea-based textured vegetable protein (TVP) and *Neurospora intermedia* biomass cultivated on grape marc (GM) or wine lees (WL). B) Schematic illustration of the cooking process for MABs, cooked at 180 °C for 5 min using a commercial hot air fryer.

Additionally, 0.80 % salt was added.

Once the infusion solution was fully absorbed by the protein base, 20.7 % (w/w) pre-emulsion was added. The pre-emulsion was prepared by dispersing 7 % methyl cellulose in 80 % cold water (4 °C) and mixing at 1800 rpm for 40 s using a high-shear thermo-mixer (HotmixPro Gastro Master), followed by the addition of 13 % sunflower oil and mixing for 1 min at 1800 rpm to obtain a semi-solid consistency. It was stored at 4 °C and used within 24 h. To improve gel strength and optimize texture, the formulation included 6.5 % (w/w) stabilizing solution (glutinous rice flour and bamboo fiber) alongside methylcellulose, which together acted synergistically to enhance water binding (Liu et al., 2023). Sunflower oil (5.75 %, w/w) was added to improve juiciness and replicate the fat content of conventional meat.

The resulting meat analogue dough was manually shaped into ~20 g balls. Samples were placed on aluminum trays and stored at 4 °C until analysis or cooking. Each batch, prepared in triplicate, was cooked in a commercial hot air fryer (COSORI, model CAF-R903) at 180 °C for 5 min (Bakhsh et al., 2021). Compared to conventional frying, air frying is known to limit thermal oxidation, reduce acrylamide and polar compound formation, maintain color and texture, preserve fatty acids, essential amino acids, and phenolic compounds, and enhance protein

digestibility (Baskaya-Sezer, 2025). Within 24 h of preparation, cooking efficiency, moisture content, color, pH, water activity (a_w), and texture were measured. Samples were freeze-dried for proximate composition, mineral content, and microstructure analysis.

2.3. Analysis

2.3.1. Proximate and mineral analysis

Proximate and mineral analysis of raw and cooked products were performed following AOAC (2016) methods. Moisture (AOAC 934.01), ash (AOAC 942.05), crude protein (Kjeldahl method, AOAC 2001.11) using a Kjeltec™ 8400 system with a nitrogen conversion factor of 6.25, and crude fat (AOAC 2003.05) by diethyl ether extraction were determined. Minerals, including phosphorus, zinc, copper, magnesium, iron, calcium, and manganese were analyzed by Inductively Coupled Plasma–Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) according to AOAC 985.01, 2006.03, and 2011.14, with quantification based on calibration curves from certified standards. Carbohydrate content was calculated by difference (De Angelis et al., 2020) and energy values estimated using Atwater factors (European Commission, 2025). For the proximate analyses three meat analogue balls were randomly selected from the same

dough formulated, and mean value of three replicates ($n = 3$) was calculated.

2.3.2. Physico-chemical properties

Color, pH, and water activity (a_w) were measured in both raw and cooked meat analogue balls. Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) were recorded using a portable colorimeter (CR-410, Konica-Minolta) calibrated with standard illuminant D65. Multiple surface points were averaged to obtain L^* (brightness), a^* (green–red), and b^* (blue–yellow) values. pH was measured in triplicate using a calibrated portable pH meter (HANNA Checker Plus) by inserting the probe into the product center. Water activity was measured at 25 °C with a water activity meter (LabMaster.aw, Novasina AG).

2.3.3. Techno-functional properties of protein ingredients and cooking characteristics of MABs

Water absorption capacity (WAC), oil absorption capacity (OAC), and rehydration capacity (RHC) of protein ingredients were assessed as per Hong, Shen, and Li (2022). For WAC, 0.6 g of ground TVP or fungal biomass was mixed with 10 mL of Milli-Q water in a pre-weighed tube, vortexed, left at room temperature for 5 min, centrifuged (3000 ×g, 30 min), drained, and reweighed. For OAC, 1 g of sample was treated similarly but rested for 30 min, with excess oil drained post-centrifugation. For RHC, protein ingredients were soaked in water (1:15 w/v) for 2 h, then drained for 1 h.

Calculations were based on the Eqs. 1 and 2:

$$\text{WAC or OAC} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{g}} \right) = \frac{m_2 - m_1 - m_0}{m_0} \quad (1)$$

where m_0 is the mass of the dry protein sample (g), m_1 is the mass of the empty container (g), and m_2 is the mass of the container with the protein sample and absorbed liquid (water or oil) (g).

$$\text{RHC} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{g}} \right) = \frac{\text{weight after rehydration} - \text{weight before rehydration}}{\text{weight before rehydration}} \quad (2)$$

WAC and RHC were expressed as grams of water per gram of protein sample, and OAC as grams of oil per gram of protein sample. All tests were in triplicate ($n = 3$).

Cooking characteristics of meat analogues balls (MABs) including cooking yield, moisture and fat retention, and diameter reduction were analyzed following Akcan et al. (2024) (Eqs. 3 to 6):

$$\text{Diameter reduction (\%)} = \frac{\text{Raw sample diameter (mm)} - \text{Cooked Sample diameter (mm)}}{\text{Raw sample diameter (mm)}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Fat Retention (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Cooked Weight (g)} \times \% \text{Fat in Cooked Sample})}{(\text{Raw Weight (g)} \times \% \text{Fat in Raw Sample})} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Moisture Retention (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Cooked Weight (g)} \times \% \text{Moisture in Cooked Sample})}{(\text{Raw Weight (g)} \times \% \text{Moisture in Raw Sample})} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Cooking yield (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Cooked Weight (g)})}{(\text{Raw Weight (g)})} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

2.3.4. Texture profile analysis of MABs

Texture profile analysis (TPA) was conducted on individual MABs (~20 g each, $n = 3$). Raw MABs, packed in partial vacuum, stored at 4 °C

were analyzed within 24 h of preparation. Cooked MABs (at 180 °C for 5 min) were allowed to rest for 30 s at room temperature (RT) before TPA analysis. All measurements were performed at RT using a TA.XTplus Texture Analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, UK) equipped with a 50 kg load cell and an HDP/PFS flat probe, operated via Exponent software (v6.1.3.0). Each sample underwent a double compression test adapted from Sun et al. (2022): pre-test speed 5 mm/s, test speed 1 mm/s. A 40 % strain was selected as produced meaningful structural changes and reproducible TPA properties values (hardness, cohesiveness, adhesiveness, springiness, and resilience), whereas higher strain levels caused sample rupture (data not shown). Texture attributes were measured in triplicate.

2.3.5. Microstructure analysis

Microstructure analysis of freeze-dried samples was performed using Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM; FEI Quanta 200, USA) in low vacuum mode (0.5 Torr) at 20 kV with a tungsten filament. Samples (~10 mm × 5 mm × 5 mm) were mounted on adhesive-coated aluminum stubs. Elemental microanalyses were conducted via Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) using an Oxford Xplore 30 detector and AZtec 6.0 software (Oxford Instruments, UK).

Prior to establishing the final protocol using ESEM in low vacuum mode, both untreated and freeze-dried samples were evaluated, and no significant microstructural differences were observed (data not shown). Although low vacuum mode allows observation of hydrated samples, the required time to reach the low vacuum working conditions for multiple samples together was considerably longer. To improve efficiency and ensure consistency, freeze-dried samples were used, avoiding further treatment.

2.4. Sensory evaluation

Fifty-two untrained panelists (26 female, 26 male; aged 18–70) participated in the sensory evaluation. Under blind, non-tasting conditions, they rated appearance, odor, texture, and overall liking on a 0–5 scale. Three types of meat analogue balls, one formulated with textured vegetable protein (TVP) and two with fungal biomass grown on wine lees (WL) and grape marc (GM), were air-fried and served hot. Samples were presented individually in sensory booths, identified by randomized three-digit codes and evaluated at room temperature (ISO 8589, 2007). Demographic data (age, gender, nationality) were also collected. For the sensory evaluation each type of cooked meat analogue ball was presented to each panelist, and mean values were calculated ($n = 52$).

2.5. Statistical analysis

Results are presented as mean ± SD ($n = 3$, unless otherwise specified). Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Pearson correlation analysis assessed relationships between variables. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All analyses were performed using OriginPro 2025 (OriginLab, USA).

Fig. 2. Main composition including A) proximate composition, B) essential minerals and C) color values of raw and cooked meat analogue balls (MABs) prepared with three alternative protein sources: TVP formulated with pea-based texturized vegetable protein; WL formulated with *N. intermedia* biomass cultivated on wine lees; GM formulated with *N. intermedia* biomass cultivated on grape marc. Mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$), with different superscript letters for the same parameter indicating significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among MABs samples according to Tukey's test.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Nutritional quality of meat analogue balls

This study evaluated key quality attributes to guide the screening and optimization of new meat analogue balls (MABs) formulations, minimally processed, and with clean-label ingredients, designed to meet growing consumer demand for healthy diets.

3.1.1. Proximate composition of MABs

Proximate composition and mineral content for raw and cooked MABs are presented in Fig. 2 (A-C). Protein-rich raw materials are crucial for developing the fibrous structure characteristic of meat analogues (Bulgaru et al., 2025). Meat analogues typically contain 4–25 % alternative proteins from legumes, grains, mushrooms, or mycoprotein (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). In this study, 21.4 % (w/w) of protein ingredient was used, either as pea-based TVP (65 % crude protein, unpublished data) or *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on wine lees (61.4 % crude protein, unpublished data) and grape marc (45.4 % crude protein as per Hoxha, Lennartsson, and Taherzadeh (2025).

Crude protein content in raw MABs ranged 30.7–35.0 % dry basis (db). The GM sample was statistically different ($p < 0.05$), whereas no significant difference was observed between the TVP and WL samples. After cooking, crude protein increased to 36.98–38.62 % db. Cooked TVP and GM samples were statistically different ($p < 0.05$), while WL sample, did not differ significantly from either samples (Fig. 2A).

Additionally, 100 g of dried sample (equivalent to a 204–216 g serving of the cooked product) could provide over 71 % of the recommended daily protein intake (50 g/day) of an average adult (2000 kcal) according to Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 (European Commission, 2025), meeting the adult requirement of 0.8 g per kg of body weight (WHO, 2007). Fungi-based products in this study offer protein content comparable to leading commercial meat analogues such as Beyond Meat™ (15.7 g per 100 g serving) (USDA, 2022) and Quorn™ (19.1 g per 100 g serving) (USDA, 2017). Unlike commercial meat analogues which contain egg white a known allergen e.g., Quorn™ (USDA, 2017), the fungi-based MABs in this study are formulated with allergen-free ingredients. Therefore, these fungi-based MABs offer a broader consumer appeal, including individuals with dietary restrictions such as vegans. However, further studies are needed to evaluate their safety, toxicological and allergenic potential, and consumer acceptance, although no adverse effects of *Neurospora* have been reported in humans or animals (Maini Rekdal et al., 2024; Perkins & Davis, 2000).

Moreover, fungi-based MABs offer sustainability benefits, as fungal protein is produced by upcycling byproducts from the wine and distillery industries. In general, alternative proteins are more cost-competitive and sustainable than animal-based ones (Munialo, Baeghbal, & Acharya, 2025), while significantly reducing greenhouse gas emissions (by 89–93 %) and land use (by 97 %) (Saget et al., 2021). In light of the study's limitation regarding the absence of direct comparisons with animal-based meat, future research should benchmark composition, texture, cooking loss, color, and microstructure to more accurately evaluate how closely these analogues mimic conventional meatballs' nutritional, structural, and sensory properties. Additionally, future research should explore *N. intermedia* potential to upcycle other side streams, creation of new food formulations with diverse protein sources, and provide comprehensive comparisons with both conventional meatballs and other novel alternatives.

Crude fat content in raw MABs ranged 21.9–22.8 % (db), with no significant differences between samples, as expected given that the identical recipe was used. Generally, fat values fell within the typical range for meat analogues containing pre-emulsions (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). Pre-emulsion is a functional ingredient, which can influence the nutritional composition, along with texture, pH, color, water-holding capacity, and cooking loss without significantly altering sensory quality (Kothuri et al., 2025). After cooking, fat content of MABs

decreased to 19.8–20.8 % db, with significant differences observed between WL and GM samples, while TVP fell between these groups ($p < 0.05$). These differences may be attributed to the type of protein ingredient used. Specifically, MABs formulated with fungal biomass grown on grape marc showed higher oil retention capacity (91.7 ± 2.46 %) compared to those made with fungal biomass grown on wine lees (86.9 ± 4.38 %) (Fig. 2A), as further discussed in the following sections.

In this study, MABs contained comparable fat levels with meat analogues of Beyond Meat™ (17.4 g per 100 g serving) (USDA, 2022), but significantly higher than Quorn™ (2.21 g per 100 g serving) (USDA, 2017). The product's fat content exceeds 28 % of the nutrient reference value (70 g/day) of an average adult intake references (2000 kcal/day) (European Commission, 2025). Fat correlated strongly with energy and ash content ($r > 0.82$, $p < 0.01$; Table S2a), indicating that fat-rich ingredients and seasonings (e.g., salt or flavorings) elevate calories and modulate mineral content through interactions with other components, particularly with proteins.

Ash content varied by protein source, with fungi-based products showing significantly higher levels (5.11–5.73 % db) than TVP-based products (4.24 % db). After cooking, ash content decreased to 3.37–3.65 % db, due to thermal processing, which can alter food matrix, influence mineral speciation and bioavailability (Barciela-Alonso & Bermejo-Barrera, 2015). Cooked TVP and GM samples did not differ significantly, while the WL was intermediate ($p < 0.05$). Overall, cooking led to a reduction in ash and fat levels, but increased protein content (Fig. S2), partially reflecting trends reported by Akcan et al. (2024), who observed proportional increases in protein, fat, and ash contents after cooking.

The product's total carbohydrates (up to 41 % db; Fig. 2A) and energy (up to 493 kcal/100 g db; Table S3) exceed 14.1 % and 24 % of the nutrient reference value (260 g/day and 2000 kcal/day) of an average adult intake references (2000 kcal/day), respectively (European Commission, 2025). Although dietary fiber was not measured in this study, mycoprotein is classified as 'high fiber' by the European Commission, providing ≥ 6 g per 100 g (European Parliament and Council, 2014), owing to its glucan-rich fungal cell walls. Its dietary fiber profile comprises approximately 12 % soluble and 88 % insoluble fibers, with a minor fraction of chitin and a predominance of glucans (Majumder et al., 2024).

3.1.2. Essential mineral content of MABs

The essential mineral content analysis of the MABs revealed significant variation influenced by both the protein source and the cooking process (Fig. 2B), affecting nutritional quality. The fungi-based products demonstrated higher levels of essential minerals compared to those formulated with the TVP. These findings suggest that fungal protein derived from oenological by-products has potential for the development of functional meat alternatives targeting micronutrient deficiencies.

Phosphorus (P) content was highest in raw WL products (1488.2 mg/100 g, db), followed by GM (798.9 mg/100 g, db) and TVP (620.5 mg/100 g, db). Cooking led to a notable decrease in P content, particularly in WL and TVP products ($p < 0.05$). Although GM products experienced a slight reduction after cooking (724.5 mg/100 g, db), they still met the recommended intake of 700 mg/day of an average adult (2000 kcal) (European Commission, 2025).

Calcium (Ca) was most abundant in raw GM products (391.2 mg/100 g, db), followed by TVP and WL. However, Ca levels declined significantly after cooking, and no significant differences were observed between TVP-based and fungi-based MABs post-cooking ($p < 0.05$). Magnesium (Mg) content was highest in raw WL products (139.73 mg/100 g, db). Cooking caused a significant reduction in Mg levels across all MABs, GM cooked products had the highest levels ($p < 0.05$). Iron (Fe) content was significantly higher in GM products, in both raw and cooked forms. Post-cooking was observed a decrease in Fe levels and no significant differences observed among products.

Zinc (Zn) was most abundant in fungi-based MABs, particularly raw

WL products had significantly highest value (20.6 mg/100 g, db) ($p < 0.05$). However, Zn decreased substantially upon cooking, and significant differences were observed across samples ($p < 0.05$). Finally, copper (Cu) and manganese (Mn) levels were highest in raw GM products (8.68 and 3.74 mg/100 g, db), followed by WL and TVP ($p < 0.05$). Both minerals decreased significantly after cooking, with no significant differences among the cooked fungi-based MABs ($p < 0.05$).

The observed variations in mineral content (Fig. S2) after cooking are likely due to differences in how minerals are bound within the food matrix and their susceptibility to leaching, oxidation, or other physicochemical heat-induced changes, including the release of metal ions from proteins due to the reduction of available carboxylic groups (Gómez, Ibanez, & Beriain, 2019). Cooking can also lead to moisture loss, protein unfolding, fiber softening, and cellular disruption, all of which influence mineral retention (Vu, Zhou, & McClements, 2022). These findings highlight the need for further research into mineral accessibility, as well as further optimization of cooking methods.

Generally, fungi-based MABs may meaningfully contribute to the recommended daily intake of essential minerals of an average adult (2000 kcal) (European Commission, 2025), with cooked products containing 823.63–936.24 mg/100 g db of total essential mineral content, offering a nutritional advantage over TVP-based MABs, which provided 700.77 mg/100 g db (Table S3).

3.2. Physico-chemical properties of meat analogue balls: Color, pH, and water activity

Color is a critical factor in consumer acceptance and product selection, which varies based on the characteristics of added ingredients (Akcan et al., 2024). To mimic meat, this study's MABs formulation incorporated 0.3 % (w/w) beetroot extract, an ingredient, which is used by leading commercial brands of meat alternatives such as Beyond Meat™ (USDA, 2022) and Impossible Foods™ (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021).

The L^* (brightness) values ranged 40.88–54.72 in raw MABs and increased after cooking to 43.97–59.66, consistently higher in TVP products (Fig. 2C). Color is affected by both the intrinsic color of ingredients and processing factors (Corrêa, da, Ferreira, & Guerra, 2023). Brightness is primarily influenced by water and fat content, and the inclusion of beetroot extract in the formulations is supposed to further enhance L^* values (Gamarrá-Castillo, Echeverry-Montaña, Marbello-Santrich, Hernández-Carrión, & Restrepo, 2022).

Significant differences in color parameters were observed between TVP-based and fungi-based MABs ($p < 0.05$). TVP samples exhibited significantly higher a^* (redness) and b^* (yellowness) values compared to fungi-based MABs (Fig. 2C). Raw products with higher fat content showed significantly lower red and yellow tones ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, increased ash levels in raw products were significantly correlated with decreased brightness, redness, and yellowness values ($p < 0.01$, Table S2b).

Color changes after cooking varied by product type: brightness (L^*) increased in TVP and GM samples but decreased in the WL sample; redness (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) increased in TVP and WL samples but decreased in the GM sample. Color changes may be influenced by beetroot extract, which is known to lose red pigmentation and develop more yellow tones when heated, contributing to brownish hues (Gamarrá-Castillo et al., 2022). Additionally, the protein sources also influenced color, as demonstrated by strong positive correlations with color parameters in cooked products ($r > 0.75$, $p < 0.01$, Table S2c), further contributing to the replication of a cooked meat-like appearance (Tan, Zhang, & McClements, 2023). pH, known to influence color development, showed a strong positive correlation with b^* (yellowness) values in both MABs raw ($r = 0.72$, Table S2b) and cooked ($r = 0.68$, Table S2c) ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the product's pH, formulated with beetroot extract colorant and the TVP or fungal protein sources, may affect pigment stability and interactions within meat analogue

matrix. Acidulants such as citric, acetic, and lactic acids are commonly used to adjust pH in meat analogues, but must be carefully applied due to their impact both on flavor and protein structure (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021).

The pH is a key quality indicator of meat, closely associated with product freshness and protein stability (Tarasevičienė et al., 2022). In this study, raw meat analogue balls (MABs) formulated with pea-based TVP and fungal biomass exhibited pH values ranging 5.70–6.06 (Table S3), which fall within the typical range reported for meat analogues (Gómez et al., 2019). GM products had a significantly lower pH compared to TVP and WL ($p < 0.05$). The pH levels increased slightly after cooking in TVP and WL products, which may be due to the formation of basic Maillard reaction products, the loss of volatile organic acids, the concentration of alkaline peptides, or the thermal breakdown of proteins and carbohydrates (Fiorentini, Kinchla, & Nolden, 2020). Conversely, the cooked GM products showed a decrease in pH (5.61), possibly due to the concentration of intrinsic organic acids resulting from moisture loss or the release of acidic degradation products during heating. Additionally, ingredients used to improve water-holding capacity may contribute to increased pH levels (Kothuri et al., 2025).

Water activity (a_w) values ranged from 0.935 to 0.910 in raw products, decreasing slightly after cooking to 0.905–0.913 (Table S3). These relatively high a_w levels may increase the risk of microbial growth and shorten shelf life, emphasizing the need for effective preservation strategies. Understanding both pH and water activity (a_w), among other factors, is essential for managing the Maillard reaction. While this reaction enhances flavor and color, it can reduce the nutritional value by modifying essential amino acids like lysine, binding key minerals such as copper, zinc, and iron, and promoting protein crosslinking through the formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) and related compounds (Zhang, Ames, Smith, Baynes, & Metz, 2009). Due to its complexity, the Maillard reaction influences sensory attributes, nutritional quality, and product stability during storage and distribution of the final products (El Hosry et al., 2025).

3.3. Techno-functional properties of protein ingredients and cooking characteristics of MABs

The techno-functional properties of the three protein sources utilized in this study, along with cooking characteristics and water holding capacity of the meat analogue balls (MABs) are presented in Table 1.

In meat alternatives, water typically comprises 50–80 % of the product, plays a vital role by influencing density, enabling biochemical reactions such as protein cross-linking, and acting as a medium for energy transfer (Gamarrá-Castillo et al., 2022). Water absorption capacity (WAC) can serve as a quality indicator of protein ingredients, contributing to a preferable texture in meat analogues (Mandliya, Pratap-Singh, Vishwakarma, Dalbhagat, & Mishra, 2022). In the present study, WAC was significantly higher in fungal proteins (5.92 to 6.51 g/g), compared to the TVP (4.22 g/g). Therefore, since methylcellulose was included at the same level in all formulations, the high juiciness observed in WL samples can likely be attributed to the greater water absorption capacity (WAC) of fungal protein. The strong negative correlation between WAC and color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) observed in both raw and cooked MABs ($r < -0.78$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2b and S2c), suggests the presence of higher levels of pigments, polyphenols, or Maillard products, polar compounds that bind water and may reduce brightness by darkening the MABs.

Oil absorption capacity (OAC) is considered an indicator of flavor and mouthfeel due to its role in oil entrapment within meat analogue matrix (Mandliya et al., 2022). To enhance juiciness, tenderness, and mouthfeel, commonly are added oils such as coconut, palm, sunflower, canola, and corn (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). In the present study, in products formulation was used sunflower oil, also was used to assess OAC. The OAC varied significantly among proteins sources, with the lowest observed in the WL sample (0.17 g/g), followed by TVP (1.78 g/g), and the highest in the GM sample (5.81 g/g) ($p < 0.05$). Since protein

Table 1

Techno-functional properties of alternative protein sources: pea-based texturized vegetable protein (TVP) and protein-rich *Neurospora intermedia* biomass cultivated on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL), and cooking characteristics of meat analogue balls (MABs) prepared from these protein sources.

Protein source	Techno-functional of alternative protein sources				
	WAC (g/g)*	OAC (g/g)*	RHC (g/g)*		
TVP	4.22 ± 0.20 ^b	1.78 ± 0.12 ^b	0.57 ± 0.11 ^b		
WL	6.51 ± 0.83 ^a	0.17 ± 0.02 ^c	1.36 ± 0.15 ^a		
GM	5.92 ± 0.43 ^a	5.81 ± 0.49 ^a	0.46 ± 0.062 ^b		
MABs	Water holding capacity and cooking characteristics of MABs				
	WHC (%)**	DR (%)***	OR (%)***	MR (%)***	CE (%)***
TVP	88.94 ± 1.20 ^a	5.82 ± 0 ^a	90.6 ± 3.18 ^a	82.9 ± 0.69 ^a	90.11 ± 0.46 ^a
WL	86.90 ± 1.35 ^a	0.11 ± 0.20 ^c	86.9 ± 4.38 ^a	77.7 ± 2.13 ^b	86.54 ± 0.31 ^c
GM	86.26 ± 0.94 ^a	3.57 ± 0 ^b	91.7 ± 2.46 ^a	79.8 ± 0.49 ^{ab}	87.64 ± 0.16 ^b

Mean ± standard deviation ($n = 3$), with different superscript letters in the same column indicating significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among MABs samples according to Tukey's test. TVP: Pea-based texturized vegetable protein and TVP-based MABs; WL: *N. intermedia* biomass grown on wine lees and WL-based MABs; GM: *N. intermedia* biomass grown on grape marc and GM-based MABs. WAC: Water Absorption Capacity; OAC: Oil Absorption Capacity; RHC: Rehydration Capacity, all measured on *protein sources. WHC: Water Holding Capacity, measured on **raw MABs. DR: Diameter Reduction; OR: Oil Retention; MR: Moisture Retention; and CE: Cooking Efficiency, calculated based on measurements *** before and after cooking of MABs.

functions. Including water and oil absorption capacities, depend on factors like amino acid composition, chemical structure, and environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, pH, and ionic strength) (Ahmad et al., 2022). Future studies should explore such parameters and how molecular and structural characteristics influence protein functionality in fungi-based meat analogues.

Rehydration capacity (RHC) refers to the ability of protein ingredients to retain water when rehydrated in excess water (Mattila, Marhendraswari, Nikinmaa, & Sozer, 2025). In this study RHC was significantly higher in the WL protein (1.36 g/g), whereas no significant differences were observed between the TVP (0.57 g/g) and GM (0.46 g/g) samples. A significant negative correlation between RHC and OAC ($r = -0.78$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2) suggests that differences in product structure and the balance between hydrophilic and hydrophobic sites, may influence water or oil absorption capacities. Additionally, water availability in the MABs matrix and the extent of interactions with pea-based TVP or fungal protein, methylcellulose, glutinous rice flour, bamboo fiber, is known to have an influence in the functional properties of proteins (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021).

Water holding capacity (WHC) reflects the ability of meat analogues to retain water during rehydration and contribute to the formation of a protein gel network, thereby influencing product juiciness (Mandliya et al., 2022). In the present study, WHC values showed slight variation among MABs, with the highest observed in TVP-based formulation (88.94 %), while fungi-based formulations showed slightly lower values: 86.90 % for WL and 86.26 % for GM. This difference may be attributed to structural disintegration during rehydration, influenced by cell structure and porosity, which aligns with the study of Mandliya et al. (2022), who reported reduced WHC when mycelium was used.

Parameters like cooking efficiency (CE), moisture retention (MR), oil retention (OR), and changes in diameter (DR) are crucial for understanding meat analogues behavior during cooking, related closely to its quality and sensory properties (Akcan et al., 2024). Moisture and oil retention are critical for achieving desirable texture, juiciness, and

flavor in meat analogues (Akcan et al., 2024; Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). In the present study, MR was highest in TVP-based MABs (82.9 %), followed by GM (79.8 %) and lowest in WL (77.7 %), with a significant differences were observed between TVP and WL samples ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, OR ranged from 86.9 % to 91.7 %, with no significant differences among samples. Notably, both MR and OR values of MABs formulated with all protein sources trialed exceeded those reported for beef meatballs by Akcan et al. (2024).

Cooking losses from liquid release and evaporation significantly impact cooking efficiency, influenced by temperature, time, sample size, and notably, the cooking method. In the present study, air frying was employed, a method known to reduce moisture loss compared to traditional frying (Télez-Morales, Rodríguez-Miranda, & Aguilar-Garay, 2024). CE ranged 86.5–90.1 %, with TVP products showing the highest CE value (90.11 %), followed by GM (87.64 %) and WL the lowest (86.54 %) ($p < 0.05$).

Product appearance, including size changes, is a key quality factor influencing consumer preference and requires careful monitoring (Akcan et al., 2024). Diameter reduction (DR) was greatest in TVP-based meat analogue balls (5.82 %), followed by GM (3.57 %) and WL (0.11 %) samples ($p < 0.05$). DR had a strong positive correlation with MR ($r = 0.88$, $p < 0.01$, Table S2c), which agrees with the study of Akcan et al. (2024), who reported that lower DR corresponds to a higher moisture retention. In addition, fungal protein sources with higher WAC were associated with lower DR, particularly WL-based MABs, as indicated by a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.83$, $p < 0.01$, Table S2c). Fungi-based MABs showed the lowest DR (0.11 % for WL, 3.57 % for GM), suggesting less structural collapse and potentially lower protein denaturation compared to TVP-based MABs. Filamentous hyphae can form a highly crosslinked, fibrous network that provides mechanical stability and elasticity, and when associated with polysaccharides, which act as natural plasticizers, they help mitigate protein unfolding and aggregation under heat (Finnigan, Theobald, & Bajka, 2025).

MR showed a strong positive correlation with both DR and CE ($r = 0.92$, $p < 0.01$, Table S2c), highlighting its critical role in cooking performance. Since protein denaturation, along with water and fat loss, contributes to a reduction in CE and DR (Akcan et al., 2024), these findings support the hypothesis that fungal proteins, particularly WL, may be more heat stable under cooking conditions. Additionally, variations in CE, DR, and MR reflect differences in structural organization and molecular interactions driven by ingredient composition, protein source, and cooking process (Kothuri et al., 2025).

3.4. Texture profile analysis of raw and cooked meat analogue balls

Texture is key to consumer acceptance in meat analogue products and guides product development, formulation, and quality control. Texture Profile Analysis (TPA) is widely used for evaluating meat products and meat substitutes (Schreuders, Schlangen, Kyriakopoulou, Boom, & Van Der Goot, 2021). In this study TPA was performed before and after cooking of MABs, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the texture attributes, presented in Fig. 3. The mouthfeel characteristics (hardness, springiness, cohesiveness) can be predicted by TPA, which can vary depending by ingredient composition, protein source, and cooking process (Kothuri et al., 2025; Nwosisi, Nandwani, & Ravi, 2019).

Hardness, measured as the peak force in the first compression, relates to the strength of gel to withstand compression, while the sensory-wise it represents the maximum force required to compress the food between the molar teeth (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015). In this study, raw MABs hardness values ranged from 0.47 to 0.51 kg with no statistically significant differences among the samples. Cooking significantly increased hardness, especially in GM (3.10 kg), followed by TVP (1.19 kg) and WL (0.91 kg) ($p < 0.05$). Sensory evaluation reflected this trend, with GM rated highest (4.02 ± 0.94), then TVP (3.35 ± 0.81), and WL lowest (1.56 ± 0.75) (Table 2). This difference is likely attributed to the

Fig. 3. Texture properties of raw and cooked meat analogue balls (MABs) prepared with alternative protein sources: pea-based texturized vegetable protein (TVP) and protein-rich *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL). Texture properties: hardness, cohesiveness, adhesiveness, springiness, and resilience) values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Different superscript letters within each raw or cooked MAB groups per each texture property indicate significant differences among samples ($p < 0.05$), as determined by Tukey's test.

protein sources, binders, and beetroot extracts, as well as their interactions, which are known to significantly influence hardness (Gamarra-Castillo et al., 2022).

Notably, in cooked GM products, protein appeared to contribute to the formation of a stronger gel network compared to TVP and WL samples, resulting in a denser structure, likely due to aggregation and cross-linking (Gravelle, Marangoni, & Barbut, 2017). It was hypothesized that the protein-to-macromolecules (fiber) ratio plays a critical role in hardness, with MABs tending to be harder when formulations contain less crude protein and higher fiber content. Additionally, the observed correlations between hardness and crude protein as well as between WAC and color, are hypothesized to reflect the role of fungal cell wall polysaccharides such as chitin and β -glucans in water and fat binding, as well as in texture formation (Kyanko, Canel, Ludemann, Pose, & Wagner, 2013). The greater hardness observed, particularly in GM products, may be attributed to their lower crude protein content and likely higher proportion of dietary fibers from filamentous fungi biomass, such as β -glucan, chitin, and chitosan (Colosimo et al., 2021). The significant negative correlation between crude protein content and hardness ($r = -0.73$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2c) further supports this observation. Gibis, Pribek, Kutzli, and Weiss (2021) also reported that higher protein levels are associated with increased porosity in heated fibers. However, further research is needed to confirm these relationships. Fat content had a significant positive correlation with hardness ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2c). Conversely, GM products showed a strong negative correlation between fat and hardness ($r = -1.00$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2d), suggesting that oil proportion influences hardness. This relationship, along with the influence of oil type and its interactions with other ingredients, warrants further investigation. Additionally, hardness may be affected by the cooking method. In this study air-frying was utilized, which is known to influence hardness by lowering starch gelatinization degree and promote crust formation (Télez-Morales et al., 2024).

Cohesiveness is defined as the ratio of the positive force area during the second compression to that of the first. In this study, raw GM products exhibited the highest cohesiveness (2.23), followed by WL (2.07), and TVP (1.19), suggesting that fungi-based MABs have superior internal bonding strength and resistance to structural breakdown. However, post-cooking, cohesiveness significantly dropped in GM (0.63)

likely due to the development of a denser and more brittle texture. In contrast, TVP (1.24) and WL (1.45) retained relatively higher cohesiveness ($p < 0.05$), potentially indicating better protein network formation and a more stable internal structure, compared to GM cooked products. The protein source plays a key role in MABs consistency and structural integrity, particularly in WL, providing MABs with enhanced resistance to disintegration under mechanical stress (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015).

Adhesiveness is defined as the negative force area during the first bite. It represents the work needed to overcome the attractive forces between the food surface and any surface that comes into contact with food (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015). In this study, all raw MBAs showed no significant differences in adhesiveness values (-0.037 to -0.020 kg-s). After cooking, adhesiveness slightly decreased across all samples (-0.006 to -0.002 kg-s), again with no significant differences. This reduction was associated with increased hardness and decreased cohesiveness ($r = -0.72$ and $r = 0.75$, $p < 0.05$, Table S2c), likely resulting from protein denaturation, matrix expansion, crust formation, and cooking loss.

Springiness is related to the relative height reduction between the 2 compressions, i.e., how well it returns to its original shape between the end of the first bite and the start of the second (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015). In this study, raw MABs showed springiness values ranging from 1.22 to 2.45, with the highest observed in GM (2.45) and WL (2.24), and the lowest in TVP (1.22). No significant differences were found. The higher values in fungi-based MABs suggest greater elasticity. Upon cooking, springiness decreased in fungi-based products, WL dropped to 1.59 and GM was significantly reduced to 0.55 ($p < 0.05$). This reduced springiness in cooked fungi-based MABs was strongly associated with higher hardness ($r = -0.97$, $p < 0.01$), and lower cohesiveness ($r = 1.00$, $p < 0.01$) (Table S2c), indicating a firmer, less elastic texture and reduced ability of the matrix to recover its shape after deformation. Conversely, TVP showed a slight increase in springiness after cooking (1.34), which along with WL, maintained relatively higher values, suggesting that these MABs may require more mastication effort (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015).

Resilience is a measurement of how the sample recovers from deformation, given by the ratio of work done during the decompression

Table 2

Sensory attributes of cooked meat analogue balls (MABs) prepared with alternative protein sources: pea-based texturized vegetable protein (TVP) and *Neurospora intermedia* biomass cultivated on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL), evaluated by untrained panelists ($n = 52$, 26 female and 26 male), under blind, non-tasting conditions.

Sensory attribute	Cooked MABs			Scale anchors
	TVP	WL	GM	
Appearance				
External color intensity	1.50 ± 0.64 ^c	3.90 ± 0.72 ^b	4.69 ± 0.54 ^a	1 – light brown; 5 – dark brown
External color uniformity	3.04 ± 1.01 ^c	3.94 ± 1.04 ^b	4.44 ± 0.89 ^a	1 – not uniform; 5 – very uniform
Internal color intensity	1.33 ± 0.71 ^c	3.83 ± 0.65 ^b	4.79 ± 0.46 ^a	1 – light brown; 5 – dark brown
Internal color uniformity	2.94 ± 0.94 ^c	3.96 ± 0.91 ^b	4.71 ± 0.54 ^a	1 – not uniform; 5 – very uniform
Moist appearance	3.33 ± 1.10 ^a	2.23 ± 1.49 ^b	2.85 ± 1.23 ^a	1 – high moisture; 5 – very dry
Uniformity of the dough	2.25 ± 1.22 ^b	2.85 ± 1.11 ^a	2.69 ± 1.32 ^{ab}	1 – very uniform; 5 – not uniform
Odor				
Legume-like	3.12 ± 1.22 ^a	1.85 ± 0.98 ^b	1.58 ± 0.82 ^b	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Soy Sauce-like	2.52 ± 1.08 ^a	2.48 ± 1.13 ^a	2.73 ± 1.32 ^a	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Meat-like	2.08 ± 1.06 ^{ab}	2.48 ± 1.20 ^a	1.96 ± 0.97 ^b	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Fungi-like	2.10 ± 1.03 ^b	3.27 ± 1.27 ^a	2.29 ± 1.26 ^b	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Smoky/Grill-like	2.37 ± 1.24 ^a	2.37 ± 1.10 ^a	2.37 ± 1.21 ^a	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Off- flavor	1.37 ± 0.69 ^a	1.50 ± 0.72 ^a	1.56 ± 0.83 ^a	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Unusual odor	1.54 ± 0.83 ^b	1.92 ± 1.01 ^{ab}	2.02 ± 1.21 ^a	1 – no detectable; 5 – extremely intense
Texture				
Texture type	2.69 ± 1.56 ^b	2.41 ± 0.89 ^b	3.66 ± 1.28 ^a	1 – characteristics of beef; 2 – juicy; 3 – fibrous; 4 – granular; 5 – dense
Hardness	3.35 ± 0.81 ^b	1.56 ± 0.75 ^c	4.02 ± 0.94 ^a	1 – very soft; 5 – very hard
Crispiness	2.52 ± 1.04 ^a	1.31 ± 0.61 ^b	2.08 ± 1.13 ^a	1 – not crispy at all; 5 – extremely crispy
Cutting resistance	2.35 ± 0.68 ^b	1.38 ± 0.77 ^c	3.83 ± 1.02 ^a	1 – very easy to cut; 5 – very difficult to cut
Overall liking	4.08 ± 0.88 ^a	2.58 ± 1.10 ^b	2.23 ± 1.08 ^b	1 – dislike extremely; 5 – like extremely

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation ($n = 52$). Different superscript letters within the same row indicate significant differences among sensory attributes ($p < 0.05$), as determined by Tukey's test.

of the first cycle relative to that measured during the initial compression. It reflects both the immediate elastic and cohesive properties of the material of the food (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015). In raw MABs, lower resilience values were observed overall; however, fungi-based products, GM (0.15) and WL (0.12), showed significantly higher resilience than TVP (0.06) ($p < 0.05$), suggesting better elastic recovery likely due to the nature of the gel network formed. After cooking, resilience increased across all samples (0.25–0.30), with no significant differences observed. Future research should investigate the amino acid composition and molecular weight distribution, known to affect resilience (Chandra & Shamasundar, 2015).

The protein source ingredients play a crucial role in shaping texture profiles, with GM likely promoting stronger gel network formation, leading to firmer and denser textures. A lower protein-to-macronutrients ratio can alter the structural matrix, leading to increased hardness. In cooked MABs, higher fat levels were linked to weaker internal bonding and diminished structural integrity, as shown by negative correlations with cohesiveness ($r = -0.85$), adhesiveness ($r = -0.62$), and springiness ($r = -0.85$) (Table S2c). These results indicate lower resistance to

structural breakdown, reduced surface adhesion, and diminished elastic recovery after deformation. Overall, the type and proportion of protein and fat, as well as their interactions within the matrix, resulted key determinants in tailoring the texture of MABs (Fig. S2).

Overall, distinct differentiation of meat analogue balls (MABs) is driven by protein source (fungal protein or pea-based TVP) and the cooking process altered nutritional composition, texture, and color (Text S1 and Fig. S2).

3.5. Microstructure of protein sources and final products (raw and cooked)

To assess the suitability of alternative protein sources for meat analogue balls (MABs) production, morphological features and elemental distribution were examined using Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS).

ESEM images (Fig. 4) revealed distinct binding behaviors across all protein sources tested. Mycelial fibers form a compact, porous, fibrous microstructure due to strong hydrophobic interactions and electrostatic repulsion (Okeudo-Cogan et al., 2023) in the fungal protein matrix (Fig. 4A).

TVP-based MABs exhibited the densest appearance, with a less fibrous structure and some porosity, whereas fungal biomass produced a rougher, dense, and porous network with a smooth, interconnected microstructure (Fig. 4B). The fungal protein structure, characterized by thin, minimally branched filaments and high protein content, has been reported to contribute to a muscle fiber-like texture in meat analogue products (Okeudo-Cogan et al., 2023).

Beyond the inherent structural features of the protein sources, ingredient interactions play a key role in shaping the structure and texture of MABs. The comparison of raw and cooked MABs revealed a looser, more open structure after cooking (Fig. 4C). Moisture content and 180 °C heat jointly influenced expansion and porosity. The uniform gel network observed in fungi-based products is likely driven by hydrophobic interactions between fibrous fungal proteins and oil. Water facilitates the formation of disulfide, hydrogen, and hydrophobic bonds, enhancing fibrous structures. Proteins also bind flavor compounds through hydrophobic forces, with occasional covalent bonds from cysteine (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). These non-covalent and covalent interactions, hydrophobic, electrostatic, and covalent, create the complex food matrix architecture (Okeudo-Cogan et al., 2023).

EDS elemental mapping of lyophilized samples revealed key elements: carbon (C), nitrogen (N), sulfur (S), oxygen (O), phosphorus (P), and sodium (Na) (Fig. 5). In fungi-based MABs, these elements were widely distributed and not strictly colocalized with hyphae. Compared with TVP, mycelial fibers showed similar C and O surface distribution, but higher S and N. In particular, S and N serve as markers for sulfur-containing amino acids and fungal proteins, with some N from fungal cell wall chitin (Maini Rekdal et al., 2023).

N was highest in fungal proteins and lower in TVP, but reduced in MABs after cooking, likely reflecting formulation proportions and protein denaturation. S, associated with cysteine and methionine, was highest in fungal proteins and fungi-based MABs but decreased post-cooking, indicating loss or rearrangement. O content increased in cooked TVP and WL, possibly due to oxidation, starch gelatinization, or exposure of oxygen-containing groups, but declined in GM, likely because oil-filled voids and displaced hydrophilic structures. In cooked MABs, C, H, and O formed larger aggregates filling voids. P was highest in fungal proteins, especially raw GM, but dropped after cooking, possibly from complexation with proteins or fats. Na remained stable between raw and cooked samples, reflecting the same amount added to formulations.

Overall, cooking reduced N, P, and S and increased C notably in GM, suggesting moisture loss, oil retention, and a denser, oil-rich structure. WL showed minimal elemental changes, indicating stronger structural

Fig. 4. ESEM images of alternative A) protein sources, including pea-based texturized vegetable protein (TVP) and *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL), along with related meat analogue balls: B) raw and C) cooked. Colors indicate key elements distribution: red represents carbon (C), green indicates nitrogen (N), and blue shows sodium (Na). Scale bar represents 250 µm. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. EDS images of alternative protein sources, including pea-based texturized vegetable protein (TVP) and *Neurospora intermedia* biomass cultivated on grape marc (GM) and wine lees (WL), along with related meat analogue balls (raw and cooked). Each column presents the relative elemental composition (from top to bottom): carbon (C), nitrogen (N), sulfur (S), oxygen (O), phosphorus (P), and sodium (Na). Scale bar represents 250 µm.

integrity, while TVP exhibited moderate shifts.

3.6. Sensory evaluation

Achieving meat-like sensory properties is key for consumer acceptance of meat substitutes. This study's sensory evaluation showed clear differences among cooked meat analogue balls (MABs) made from TVP and fungal protein sources. Additionally, the sensory attributes of fungi-based MABs varied significantly depending on the substrate on which the *Neurospora intermedia* biomass was cultivated (Table 2). The visual appearances of the raw and cooked MABs are presented in Fig. S1.

Acceptance of meat substitutes is strongly influenced by appearance and flavor. Color uniformity and intensity were significantly highest in GM, which also had the darkest appearance; WL showed moderate values, while TVP had the lowest uniformity and intensity, appearing the lightest ($p < 0.05$). The color evaluated by panelists was consistent with the CIELab results (Fig. 2C). The darker color in fungi-based products likely resulted from Maillard reactions involving *N. intermedia* (Maini Rekdal et al., 2024). Additionally, these color differences reflect variations in protein source, ingredient interactions, and products processing.

While the darker color of the fungal proteins originates from the raw material, future work will explore decolorization strategies using activated carbon, macroporous resins, or magnetic chitosan microspheres to enhance color and sensory quality, while preserving functional properties.

Moist appearance was rated significantly higher in TVP (3.33 ± 1.10) and GM (2.85 ± 1.23) compared to WL (2.23 ± 1.48); however, the high standard deviation indicates greater variability in visual perception ($p < 0.05$). Dough uniformity also varied significantly: WL scored highest (2.85 ± 1.11), TVP lowest (2.25 ± 1.22), and GM (2.69 ± 1.32) showed moderate but more variable ratings ($p < 0.05$).

TVP-based MABs had the strongest legume-like odor (3.12 ± 1.22), characteristic of pea protein, while fungi-based products scored lower (1.58 and 1.85). Soy sauce-like odor was consistent, with GM rated higher but with more variability (2.73 ± 1.32). Meaty aroma mimicry was more pronounced in WL (2.48 ± 1.20), intermediate in TVP (2.08 ± 1.06), and the lowest GM (1.96 ± 0.97) ($p < 0.05$). Meaty flavor is indicative of sulfur-containing amino acids and glutamic acid, which contribute to a characteristic umami taste (Trinci, 1994). Soy sauce and meat-like odors correlated with fungi-like ($p < 0.05$) and smoky/grill-like notes ($p < 0.01$). WL had a significantly stronger fungi-like aroma (3.27 ± 1.27), while GM (2.29 ± 1.26) and TVP (2.10 ± 1.03) showed no significant difference among them. Fungi-like odor showed a positive correlation with soy sauce and unusual odors ($p < 0.05$), as well with meat-like and smoky/grill aromas ($p < 0.01$).

The smoky/grill odor intensity was similar across all samples (2.37 ± 1.10). Off-flavor scores were low overall, indicating clean flavor profiles. GM exhibited the strongest perception of unusual odors (2.02 ± 1.21) ($p < 0.05$).

Hardness differed significantly: GM was firmest (4.02 ± 0.90), TVP moderate (3.35 ± 0.81), and WL softest (1.56 ± 0.74), consistent with TPA analysis results (Fig. 3). Cutting resistance was highest in GM (3.83 ± 1.02), moderate in TVP (2.35 ± 0.68), and lowest in WL (1.38 ± 0.77), reflecting structural differences. Texture showed a significant positive correlation with hardness and cutting resistance ($p < 0.01$). Crispiness was rated the lowest in WL (1.31 ± 0.61), while TVP (2.52 ± 1.04) and GM (2.08 ± 1.12) had a higher rating, indicating a crispier surface.

Overall liking differed significantly among samples, TVP scored highest (4.08 ± 0.88), showing strong consumer acceptance and consistent appeal, while fungi-based WL (2.58 ± 1.08) and GM (2.23 ± 1.08) scored lower with more variable responses ($p < 0.05$). These liking scores indicate limited acceptability from a consumer perspective, aligning with the broader sensory-acceptance challenges commonly observed for novel protein sources. Liking correlated significantly with

color intensity and uniformity, smoky/grill-like and legume-like odors, cutting resistance, crispiness, and moist appearance ($p < 0.05$) (Table S4), favoring softer, moist, and less intensely colored samples with legume-like aroma.

In Fig. 6 are presented panelist texture ratings. TVP was described as “granular” with “beef-like” characteristics, indicating a coarse texture and visual similarity to beef. WL was noted as “juicy” and “fibrous,” resembling moist muscle, while GM was “dense” and “fibrous,” reflecting a compact structure. Combining proteins with non-protein binders often reduced juiciness (Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). WL fungal protein may better replicate juicy, fibrous textures suitable for moist or shredded meat alternatives such as pulled meat, stir-fry strips, fajita fillings, or BBQ-style sandwiches. In contrast, GM fungal protein offers a denser, more compact texture, aligning with structured applications like meatloaf, stuffed peppers, grilled skewers, deli-style slices, or sausage-type products. Significant gender effects were observed, with males rating texture ($p < 0.01$) and crispiness ($p < 0.05$) higher (Table S3). Similar trends have been reported for fungi-based patties produced from *Neurospora intermedia* cultivated on bread (Hellwig et al., 2020).

These results offer insights for reformulation strategies aimed at improving sensory attributes that currently hinder the overall acceptance of fungi-based MABs. Although TVP benefits from consumer familiarity and higher acceptance, increasing the appeal of fungi-based MABs formulated with *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on wine lees and grape marc necessitates effective consumer education and awareness.

However, this study's conclusions on flavor, texture, and consumer acceptability are limited, since the sensory test was conducted under blind conditions with untrained panelists and without tasting. Future work should therefore include full sensory evaluation and consumer acceptance testing.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights *Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on wine lees and grape marc as a protein-rich ingredient for meat analogues with potential nutritional claims, functional and sustainable alternative protein source to commercial plant-based alternatives. Fungi-based meat analogue blends (MABs) were richer in essential minerals than TVP-based products, highlighting their potential as a nutritionally superior option to meet daily mineral requirements. *Neurospora intermedia* biomass demonstrated excellent water absorption and oil retention, contributing to improved cooking performance, reduced shrinkage, and enhanced juiciness in the final products. Meat alternatives using fungal

Fig. 6. Perceived mimicry of texture characteristics: granular, dense, juicy, beef, and fibrous, for cooked MABs prepared with alternative protein sources: TVP pea-based texturized vegetable protein; WL (*Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on wine lees); GM (*Neurospora intermedia* biomass grown on grape marc).

proteins achieved firmer, chewier, and more cohesive textures that closely mimic real meat, due to the biomass's filamentous, fibrous structure forming compact, muscle-like networks.

Sensory evaluation showed that while TVP-based products benefit from greater consumer familiarity, fungi-based products offer distinctive fibrous textures, juiciness and more pronounced meat-like aromas. However, variability in consumer perception indicates the need for further optimization and increased consumer exposure. Despite moderate consumer liking, fungi-based MABs demonstrated promising nutritional quality, superior functional performance, and favorable textural properties compared with commercial TVP-based alternatives.

These findings support the feasibility of integrating *N. intermedia* biomass into the food industry as a novel alternative protein source that can improve the quality, functionality, and appeal of meat analogues. Such incorporation may also contribute to a circular bioeconomy, diversify the range of meat alternatives, and deliver environmental and nutritional benefits. Future research should prioritize assessing safety, allergenicity, protein digestibility, and nutrient bioavailability, while also enhancing flavor, shelf-life, color, and overall product performance. Developing hybrid formulations and expanding the product range will be essential for meeting consumer expectations and maximizing the commercialization potential of fungi-based foods.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luziana Hoxha: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ivana Sucic:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad J. Taherzadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Matteo Marangon:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethics statement

All sensory evaluation procedures involving human participants (adults) were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the Ethics Committee for Research at the University of Padova. Ethical request (no. 2025/07) for this study was approved on 9 April 2025, approval Prot. n. 0002448. The study complied with the EU Regulation 2016/679 on the protection and processing of personal data. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, with full disclosure of the study's purpose, procedures, and any potential risks. Participation was entirely voluntary, with no coercion, and participants retained the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and privacy of participant data were strictly maintained throughout the research.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2025.104409>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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